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Failed Diplomacy: St Lubin's Mission to Maratha Court

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Relations of French East India Company's relations with Marathas is not as celebrated and debated in Indian colonial history as of Mysore or Hyderabad. The present paper analytically reveals that through diplomatic missions French tried to associate closely with the Marathas. So that they can use it as one of the main stay of French hope of *revanche* in India. During the late Eighteenth century they kept negotiating with the Maratha powers to form a formidable Alliance.

The governor of French possessions in India, M. Law de Lauriston has been an advocate of Franco- Maratha alliance. Since his arrival in India, Law maintained correspondence with different fractions of Marathas with the hope that whenever the opportune moment will arrive he will be able to bring these Maratha chiefs closer to French and put forth a combined force against the English in India. Marathas too wanted to cultivate the friendship of French to repulse the increasing English dominance and had forwarded certain proposals of friendship to Law, which in turn were forwarded to home government by him for consideration.

French governments initiatives : The Maratha proposals sent by Law through Beylie reached France in early 1776. War had just broken out between England and her American colonies. The situation seemed propitious for France to avenge her defeat in 1763. Though the decision to intervene in the War was still in its infancy, Vergennes, the French minister for Foreign Affairs, advised Sartine, the Minister of Marine, to establish contact with the Government of Poona. Sartine, who had been already approached by Lubin on this subject, decided to entrust him with the mission. ¹Lubin's plan was a treaty with the Marathas, by which the French would furnish them a corps of troops, consisting of 2,400 soldiers. These troops would be divided into two regiments. The first would be composed of 1,200 men, named the Regiment of Alliance, which would serve the Marathas and always maintain its full strength. The second would be stationed at Pondicherry and utilized for recruiting the Regiment of Alliance.² The Marathas, Lubin underscored, possessed a decided superiority over the English in the open field. The French artillery would give the Marathas a decisive advantage over the English in siege operations.

On March 26, 1776, Sartine informed Lubin of the King's decision to employ him as accredited envoy to negotiate a treaty of commerce with the Marathas at Poona.³ St. Lubin was entrusted with two letters. In the first letter, the King of France assured the Peshwa that the former had no ambition for making territorial acquisitions in Hindusthan. His Majesty's real intentions were only to establish commerce between the two Nations.⁴ The second letter was from Sartine and was addressed to Nana Fadnavis, First Minister of the Maratha Empire.⁵ On April 22, St. Lubin received the contents of his mission.⁶ He was to sign a treaty of commerce consisting of the following four articles:⁷

1. There should exist between the French and the Marathas a perpetual friendship whereby the French would render all possible service to the Marathas, who, in turn, would guarantee protection to French possessions in Hindusthan against any enemy whatsoever;

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2. Maratha traders would be exempt from customs duties in all the French dominions, present and future, and vice- versa;
3. Maratha ships will have free access into all French ports and the same will apply to French ships at Maratha ports;
4. And lastly, Maratha vessels would be under French protection at all times in all the ports under the rule of that Government and vice-versa.⁸

In explaining Article 1, Lubin had to underscore that since France was presently at peace with other nations (meaning England), His Majesty could not enter into an alliance hostile to any of them.⁹ But, if any Power provoked hostilities and took up arms, the King would then unite his forces with those of the King of the Marathas to punish the common enemy.¹⁰ On this understanding, Lubin was to negotiate a conditional treaty of offensive and defensive alliance between the two Crowns against any aggressor.¹¹ Pending the ratification of these terms by His Majesty, the King of France, St. Lubin was to procure from the Marathas a guarantee of provisional protection to all the French establishments in India against the attacks of any enemy.¹² In return, His Majesty would permit His ship-owners to trade in arms and munitions with the Marathas, a relationship befitting the two nations bound by friendship and common interests.¹³

As a precondition of this commercial bond, St. Lubin was instructed to request the grant of suitable sites in the Maratha ports for the establishment of commercial houses, as well as for the construction of vessels.

Events at the Poona court : On February 22, 1777, St. Lubin reached Poona and was received by the Peshwa with all the honors befitting the dignity of the envoy of the King of France.¹⁴ This was in contrast of the instruction given to him by the minister to follow extreme secrecy in negotiations. St Lubin arrived 'riding an elephant and accompanied by seven or eight officers in palanquins'.¹⁵ He was given an audience with the Peshwa on 8th may. On June 27, Nana Fadnavis delivered the Peshwa's reply to Louis XVI's letter. The Peshwa expressed his great pleasure in accepting the French King's friendship, and gave the latter an assurance about his own. He also confirmed that the French could obtain from the Maratha Government all the assistance they needed. Nana Fadnavis sent his reply to Sartine's letter. M. Pascal de Santy carried the responses back to France.¹⁶

With regard to the conditional treaty, the Marathas promised to place at St. Lubin's disposal, a cavalry force of 25,000 men in case of hostilities against the French establishments in India. On their part, the French were to dispatch a force of 2,500 men to assist the Marathas as soon as war was declared between France and England in Europe. St Lubin had also planned for the landing of these troops at a Portuguese harbor and requested for the same to the Captain General of Goa.¹⁷

The French request for the grant of suitable sites in the Maratha ports for the establishment of commercial houses was assured. St. Lubin sent his reports to the Minister.

The smooth course of negotiations between the French and Marathas was for a while disrupted by English intrigues.¹⁸ Nevertheless, St. Lubin continued to use all the diplomatic nuances to influence the Peshwa and his Council. He revealed them the intricacies of English politique in India. The English could never defeat the Marathas if the latter remained united. Hence, the English were trying to divide and weaken them by sowing the seeds of discord between the different factions. This motive impelled the English to foment quarrels between the Marathas and Haider Ali.

St Lubin also kept Bellecombe, governor of Pondicherry informed about the transactions taking place by a letter.¹⁹ Bellecombe, however, did not find any benefit by the commercial treaty concluded by Lubin as he was in favour of a military alliance with Mysore.²⁰ Also, he betrays jealousy for Lubin as he was independently negotiating a treaty

with Marathas on behalf of French King. He felt that his position and dignity as the Governor of whole French dominions in India was compromised.²¹ He was right when he concludes that having the Marathas and Haider Ali both on board is a must for any success of French designs in India.²²

Meanwhile, Bombay government grew anxious of French machination and expressed their disappointment to Nana. To which he gave a dubious reply:

*theirs being a sovereign state, every power desirous of sending ambassadors to cultivate in friendship and seek its connection; to refuse admission to the ambassadors of the French monarch or other powers charged with proposition of friendship from their masters would be highly improper, and not to hear their representation would be inconsistent with the credit and dignity of the state.*²³

Given the uncertain nature of reply, now Bombay government registered their protest through official channel, i.e. by English agent at the Poona darbar, Mr Mostyn. He, in person, informed Minister Sakharam Bapu that friendship with the France has definitely caused a breach of trust and has injured the honourable company.²⁴

English, for a time being, with the help of Moroba and Ragunathrao were able to check these activities, Moroba with help of Tkoji Holker had captured Poona and Nana, along with Peshwa Sawai Madhavrao, had to retreat to Purandar. But soon both the parties reconciled and St Lubin again started with his plans.

Lubin, in line with the instructions he received, implored the Marathas to reconcile their differences with Haider Ali for the moment, and make a united stand against a more menacing enemy, the English. The Peshwa agreed to terminate hostilities with Mysore, but he demanded the assistance of the King of France to reduce Bombay, Salsette, Surat and Bhadoch (190 miles north of Bombay). In return for their services, the Peshwa would cede Bombay and Surat to the French, while Salsette and Bhadoch would return to the Marathas. Lubin hurriedly dispatched this entire information through M. Pascal de Santy to France. St. Lubin was invited to Purandhar to finalize the agreement.²⁵

The negotiations for the supply of French troops to expel the English from India were concluded after prolonged discussions between Lubin and the representatives of the Maratha government at Poona, namely, Sakharam Bapu, Nana and Krishnarao. War against the English would commence as soon as France furnished her contingent of 2,500 men. The Marathas undertook to defray the expenses of the French troops—their levy, armament, equipment, maintenance, transport and pay. They were to supply the wood for the construction of the French fleet, composed of one vessel of 64 guns, four frigates of 32, sixteen corvettes of 16, including the other resources. This fleet armed, equipped and maintained by the King of France and attached to the French contingent of 2,500 men, would be stationed at the Isle of France under the orders of the Envoy Plenipotentiary of the King of France to the Maratha Court, who would assume the command of all the troops [land and naval] which would be called “troops of alliance”. St. Lubin planned to proceed to France himself to explain all the terms of the treaty. The Peshwa sent a letter to the King of France, requesting him for an expeditious reply. He also solicited St. Lubin’s return to his Court, in order that the latter may serve as the link of friendship between the two Crowns.

English Response to St Lubin’s Mission : “Hitherto no agreement had been concluded between him and this darbar, neither shall any be made here after, and I will never hold with him or his nation, any sort of friendship...”³¹

Mahadji Sindhia wrote to Hastings that he has persuaded Nana and Sakharam Bapu to cease friendliness with French and both have adhered to the suggestion.³² Though English were able to check the power of Nana for time being but their hope of getting a pro-English administration at Poona failed as soon Maratha factions reconciled and came together.³³ St Lubin, too, remained in Poona itself.

Throughout the negotiations, St Lubin maintained regular correspondence with French consul at Surat, M. Briancourt.³⁴ It was from Briancourt that St Lubin came to know about the English designs on Bessein.³⁵

In fact, the French with the assistance of the Marathas might have succeeded in defeating the English, and it was the reality of this threat which drove the English to frustrate their plans.

*'We regard the Marathas as the only native and the French as the only Foreign Power in the East Indies, capable of affecting the influence which the English nation has acquired in it...'*³⁶

In addition, the English were aware of the formidable strength of Haider Ali. The latter would seize this opportunity to attack the English in the South. To avoid such a concerted attack, the English disrupted the Franco-Maratha alliance and exacted a promise from the new Maratha leader at Poona, Raghoba, to repudiate all connections with France. Thus, I will conclude that the delay in the Franco-Maratha negotiations exacerbated by the military insufficiency of the French in India, and the circum-spect disposition of the Versailles government, foiled the vigorous attempts of French plenipotentiaries in India to erect a firm bond between the French and their Maratha connection.

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